

IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF MAKING COMPLEX FERTILIZERS ON LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

Akramova Diyora Mirzohid qizi

Namangan Institute of Engineering and Construction

Master student

Annotation: This article provides information on how to obtain complex fertilizers and their types

Keywords: Mineral fertilizers, trace elements, Phosphorus, Potassium, Chile nitrate, Sodium nitrate, nitrogen.

INTRODUCTION

About 10% of the earth's surface is covered by agricultural crops. It is impossible to expand the area under crops. But the population of the planet is constantly growing, and it is time to further increase productivity to provide them with food. One of the most important ways to do this is to use mineral fertilizers. Fertilizer is a substance designed to improve plant nutrition and increase soil fertility.

Mineral fertilizers are salts and other inorganic, industrial and mineral products that contain elements necessary for plant development and soil fertility and are used for stable and high yields.

More than 70 chemical elements are involved in the formation of plant tissue, its growth and development. The most important of these are carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen, which make up 90% of the dry mass of a plant; the most important of which are carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen, which make up 90% of the total mass of the plant; Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, sulfur, sodium and calcium make up 8-9% of the plant mass. These ten elements are called macro-elements. The remaining 1-2% is iron, copper, manganese, zinc, molybdenum, cobalt and others.

These plants need very small amounts (0.001-0.0001%). That is why they are called trace elements.

Plants get most of the carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen from these elements from air and water, while they get the rest from the soil. Most of the elements that the plant receives do not return to the soil, but are removed by the crop. For example, 1 ton of corn carries 14 kg of nitrogen, 2.5 kg of phosphorus, 3.5 kg of potassium, 1.5 kg of sulfur from the soil. Much of the soil elements are washed away by water and interact with soil components to make the plant unable to assimilate. As a result, there is a shortage of plant nutrients in arable lands, and soil fertility decreases. If these lost elements are not replaced by fertilizers, the yield will drop sharply.

Therefore, great attention is paid to the production of fertilizers. Due to the use of fertilizers it will be possible to increase the yield of agricultural crops by 50-60%. For example, about a quarter of the food on the planet and about half of the cotton is obtained only from fertilizers. The nutrients in fertilizers, especially nitrogen, play a major role in the mineral nutrition of plants (1 It is a component of proteins and nucleic acids. Nitrogen is also a component of photosynthesis in plants - chlorophyll, which plants use to synthesize organic matter from inorganic substances.

Phosphorus plays a major role in plant respiration and reproduction. It contains substances (enzymes, vitamins, etc.) that are important in the life of the plant. In particular, it is a complex protein-nucleoprotein found in seeds.

Chromosomes that preserve and pass on hereditary traits are made up of nucleoproteins. Phosphorus plays a key role in the high grain content of cereals. It increases the resistance of plants to cold, drought and has a positive effect on the reproduction of essential nutrients. For example, it leads to an increase in starch in potatoes and sucrose in sugar beets.

Potassium plays an important role in regulating the vital processes that take place in the plant. It improves the water regime in the plant, is involved in the formation of carbohydrates and metabolism. Dry plant stems contain up to 4-5% of

potassium, and the ash from the burning of leaves contains up to 30-60% of potassium.

Mineral fertilizers are mainly used in agriculture, for planting in crops in order to increase productivity. The second major industry where fertilizers are used is the chemical industry. In particular, sodium and potassium salts, such as Cl , KCl . Soda, hydrochloric acid, potash, caustic soda, caustic potash are raw materials for production. Na_2SO_4 is a raw material in the production of glass, sodium sulfide, fluoride, potassium and sodium dichromate, sodium phosphate.

In the field of metallurgy, fertilizers are used in ore beneficiation, liquefaction of metals, extraction of metals by electrolysis, metal surface treatment, welding of metals and alloys. In particular, sodium sulfate is the main raw material in the production of glass.

METHOD AND TECHNOLOGY

Chile Saltpeter - Obtained on the basis of natural layers of guano in Chile. After the synthesis of synthetic aerospace, nitrates are prepared on an industrial basis. The share of nitrate fertilizers in the range of nitrogen fertilizers is very small (about 1%). However, it is important to get acquainted with them in terms of soil properties and planting types.

- Chile Saltpeter - Obtained on the basis of natural layers of guano in Chile. After the synthesis of synthetic aerospace, nitrates are prepared on an industrial basis. The share of nitrate fertilizers in the range of nitrogen fertilizers is very small (about 1%). However, it is important to get acquainted with them in terms of soil properties and planting types.

Sodium nitrate

- - NaNO_3 . In the production of nitric acid is obtained on the basis of absorption of nitrogen oxides by soda or alkali:

or

- $2 \text{NaOH} + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2 = 2 \text{NaN}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- $2 \text{NaOH} + 2 \text{NO}_2 = \text{NaN}_3 + \text{NaN}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- To convert nitrites to nitrate, the mixture is treated with a weak HNO :
- $3 \text{NaN}_2 + 2 \text{HNO} = 3 \text{NaN}_3 + 2 \text{NO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- The solution is neutralized, evaporated, and after centrifugation, a white or whitish granular salt is obtained. It contains 15-16% nitrogen, is highly soluble in water, and has a high hygroscopicity.

CONCLUSION

Some crops (such as rhizomes) are very demanding on nitrogen fertilizers, which contain sodium, which improves yields as well as product quality. Studies show that the sodium in the fertilizer allows more sugar to flow from the leaf to the root.

When calcium nitrate is introduced into acidic soils, along with the decrease in acidity, the physical properties of the soil also improve because calcium coagulates the soil colloids.

References:

1. Gerasimov I P ecological problems in vrrshloy nostoyashiy ibudushey geografii mir M Nauka 1985
2. Izrael 'Yu A ecology iconrol sostoyaniya prirodnoy sred' M Gidrameteozdat 1984
3. Monitoring of the natural environment in the Aral Sea basin L Hydrometedizdat 1991
4. Tukhtaev A Khamidov A Basics of ecology and nature protection Tashkent